

Digitalization of Event Management

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Abstract

The last few years have seen instantaneous growth in Event management. This paper attempts to study how a digital technology implementation makes it easier to plan an event without any hindrance. The objective of this paper is to know how and why digital event management is needed in India. This study includes detailed information about the origin, development, role, recommendation suggestions of both traditional and digital event management system. Considering the existing problems relating to event management, how a technology is being developed in the form of online web portals and mobile applications. This paper also gives information regarding what are the various types of applications developed and how successful it is in organizing and conducting an event compared to the old method of event planning.

Keywords: Event Management, Digital technology, Web portals, Smart phone applications.

Introduction

According to Professor Philip Kotler, Events are defined as occurrences designed to communicate particular messages to target audience.

In India, events such as festivals, wedding ceremonies, etc. play a huge role, which has resulted in event Management industries to rise. With the increase of events at a higher rate, it is difficult to manage using traditional methods such as spreadsheets, manpower, and more. When we are referring to events, we include a broad range of genres, like workshops, presentations, conferences, seminars, fairs and festivals, business and corporate events, government, and civic events, etc. Current approaches to Event Management Systems cover a range of these kinds of events. Many numbers of people are working clueless under different unorganized teams. Everything is manual and lacks a digital approach. The verification and validation mechanism is absent.

To overcome the drawbacks of the traditional Event planning method, a new Smart Event Management System has been introduced, which uses modern technology for managing various tasks and

planning duties for employees, customers, location, transportation, and others. With the help of this new technology, the distances between the customer and management team have reduced and standards of the events have increased.

Conceptual Background

“Event Management is the process of creatively applying necessary professional skills in organizing a focused event for a target audience to achieve the desired objective”.

Event management as a separate industry started to surface in the 20th century, where people no longer relied upon limited resources and needed the hands of professionals in carrying out diversified events. The importance of face to face meetings and massive events began growing with the advent of industrialization, and the rise of globalization put the final stamp on the origin of event management to rise as an independent industry.

The essence of event management has always been to inspire people to come together for collective and innovative collaboration. Right from décor to lighting, furniture, centrepieces, even having the right music, and gifts are designed suitably. Today, events are all about adding the right sparkle and ambiance.

Apart from the change in accession and objective in event management, technology has a huge role to play in the evolution of event management. It has not only brought the world closer, but it has also bridged gaps between time and space. The evolution of technology has also introduced various innovative ways of reaching out to people required. Smartphones, desktop applications, mobile applications have made events more efficient and manageable.

From a business perspective, events have pre-eminence. Conducting marketing activities occasionally provide an incredible opportunity to promote one’s business. The more popular a brand becomes, and lesser apprehensions with the people. Proper event management is vital for any successful event.

Paramount of Event Management

Saves you time and money

By appointing an event management company to plan your events, you will save time and money. An event management company will have connections with hotels, venues, and suppliers and will get you excellent deals helping you to save your time and money.

Gives you creative ideas and successful event formats

Event planners will have new and innovative ideas for your events, and the arrangements that is tried and tested are implemented with specific changes as per the client requirements, which will give the guaranteed success of the event.

Expert Planning and budget management

Proper Scheduled planning emphasises to a flawlessly executed event. A successful event requires a detailed plan and a budget that will be followed. An event management company will create these. The budget for the event will be constituted by a trained event planner that has good knowledge about the costs involved and the variations that may occur.

Gives your attendees a professional outcome

Event management companies use varieties of tools and applications that help them to communicate with attendees smoothly and professionally. It can be anything from creating a specific website that has information about your entire events such as location, chief guests, attendee list, schedules, and many more – to taking feedback from the attendees about the event are the same platform.

Professional delivery on the day

The two most crucial elements for the success of an event are firstly preparing a detailed event plan for all. And secondly, having a well-instructed and experienced team managed by an event organizer taking responsibility for the overall execution of the plan.

Overseeing the risk factor and keeping everyone safe

Risks are uncertainties and there can be any unexpected occurrences that may arise and cause harm for any attendees or the organizers like power failure, unexpected fire, or a medical emergency which may have a unpleasant outcome. And having an event management company will oversee all these hindrances and be prepared for it earlier which will help in smooth flow of an event.

Organisation Personnel

The number of people involved in organizing an event depends upon its dimension and range. While conducting a small activity may call for only a few people, organizing a large scale event may require several thousands of them. Technical staffs involved in conducting an event are: Event co-ordinator

- Event manager
- Ticket sales manager
- Catering manager
- Chief electrician
- Lighting operator
- Sound operator
- Stage manager
- Costume designer
- Marketing manager

Classification of Events

Private Events

Private events are those which are conducted by individuals who have an occasion and a list of people who want to show up on the date of an event.

- Weddings
- Birthday parties
- Festival gatherings
- Ceremonies

Corporate Events

Corporate events are used by business organizations to market their companies brand and products such as

- Business dinners
- Conferences
- Seminars
- Product launches
- Meetings
- Trade shows
- Corporate Board Meetings
- Yearend functions

A business will use corporate events to build professional relationships between employees and employers to have better communication between different levels of management. Corporate events will be used by all sizes of businesses, develop a brand image in the eyes of the buyers, and retain existing suppliers and customers.

Social/Charitable Events

Charity events are used for individuals to raise money for a charity of their choice such as

1. Society balls
2. Sports events
3. Charitable auctions

Some charity events may ask for sponsors to raise money for charity. There are many types of events for raising funds such as

- Sponsored runs
- Sponsored cycling
- Sponsored walks
- Marathon, and much more.

Sponsorship refers to give and takes deal between a non-profit and a profit-oriented business organization. The business donates money for the expenses related to the charity event, and in return, the charity event gives the sponsoring company low-cost publicity and market exposure.

Event Management Software (EMS)

Event management software (EMS) is a single solution that helps event organizers in achieving success through all aspects of events—from event registration, event check-in event promotion, and reporting. Event management software includes all the tools that are required by an event organizer to perform his work comfortably, instantaneously, securely, and affluently.

Reasons for Adopting Event Management Application

Nowadays, an event management app or software has become an essential part of conducting all the events mainly due to the augmentation of the event planning and management industry. Multitudinous tasks to organize an event or multiple events can be made less pressurizing using an event management application.

Getting an organized team

An event management platform can work reverence to get an organized team, enable compelling collaboration, and reduce miscommunication. There are frequently many folks, or collaborators, involved in organizing an event, such as Administrator, Event Manager, Email Marketer and Onsite Coordinator. The event platform will assure that tasks are designated, communication is clear, and work gets done without prolonging among the collaborators. At any time, the work is overseen by the event organizer. Information is secured among the collaborators.

Create the Best Online Registration Experience

Before organizing an event without an event management app, they used Google Forms for registrations, questionnaires, and surveys. The entered information would then be analyzed in Excel spreadsheets. Many would-be perused and processed manually. That took a colossal amount of time. Errors happened more frequently.

An event management app can create highly personalized forms, distinctive tickets that match promotional needs, and communicate promptly and accurately.

Manage Your Attendees with CRM

With CRM, attendee information is centralized in a single platform where one can search for what they require in a juncture. Furthermore, they can access all transactions, registrations, attendance, communications, memberships, referral, personal preferences, feedback, etc. information of a contact.

Maximize Attendee Engagement

After an individual has purchased an event ticket, he or she will become a registrant. That doesn't assure that he or she will eventually become an attendee.

One of the quick fix is to engage the registrants. An event management application can be used to send scheduled messages, conundrum, newsletters, reminders, and so on.

Control budget

With event management a platform that incorporates financial aid, formulation of budget and apprehend expenses and incomes will be much easier.

Often, there are unexpected payments that sometimes not recorded. It will cause difference in event accounting and a lot of headaches for organizer.

Analyze Event Success

While analyzing an Event Success sometimes, organizers can connect the wrong factors to success. It might lead to not-so-successful events. Event management software is helpful in evaluating the event success or failure and learning valuable lessons.

For most event planners, the pressure to condone needs them to have access to details of ticket sales, cost, profits, etc. This report will be helpful when it comes to getting an event sponsorship.

Manage Multiple Events Simultaneously

An event management application will help to manage numerous events accurately. Event administrators and collaborators can manage various events under an organization. Most tasks are set up and automated with assignments. Once you elect and plan out strategy, you can automatically execute the task by setting up workflows. Only thing remaining is to input data and updates, as well as monitor events' status and watch analytics.

Duplicate the Success

With an event management platform, one can simulate their previous event success with saved workflows, and an entrenched framework. It is important to standardize event planning and management process so that any event team in organization can follow for future events and deliver consistently good results.

Pre-Eminent Event Management application

1. Whova All-In-One Event Management Application

Whova is an award-winning event management application that helps event organizers to save time and tries to offer the best experience to the attendees. Whova tries to make your event attendees ten times happier by helping them to participate, interact, and build better connections.

By using whova, one can save 60% of their time by managing event strategy and allow you to focus on tasks that require more time and attention. With the help of this event management application for promotion, the investors also get good exposure, and sponsors can demonstrate with various opportunities ingrained within the app, resulting in a better return on investment. Whova is suggested to all the planners for planning different scale of events. Try Whova, if you're tired of other event management apps that keep on crashing and don't offer you much of the features required.

2. Eventbrite

Eventbrite is a popular event management application that is used for all kinds of events ranging from small meetings to large concerts. This app helps the user to personalize and allows people to know all details regarding the occasion. The individual can register from their phones and can use it to send email confirmations and reminders.

The application charges an extra 2.5% of the ticket price plus \$1.99 per ticket. While Eventbrite is very popular among event managers, but some think the fee is a bit pricey compared to other all-in-one event planning software.

3. Trello

Trello is a project management software. If you want to have a “to-do” “doing” and “done” list, you'll love Trello. It has a solid optical confluence, simple usage, and teamworking features.

Though Trello has substantial communication, it's not recommendable when the user wants a brief overview of the event management process. It can only give you details regarding tasks completed and yet to be done but not a summarized views of the event activities. It is a well-organized tool to track the progress of each task. But it's hard to see the entire project status for event or conference management.

4. Social Tables

Social tables simplify seating chart management, room layout design, guest check-in, and event management tracking. It is an ideal application which can be used by the detailed-oriented event planners -- especially for small/mid-size social events like weddings. Organizers can also communicate with caterers, venue providers, and co-workers through the system. If you're looking for a check-in tool over a seating chart management tool for corporate events like seminars, conferences, business meetings, etc. first check whether your online registration system or conference management software already includes a check-in feature.

5. Super Planner

Every event or a conference is sums total of the marketing, logistics, event plan, and layout, and most importantly the budget. Best of the planners keep things within budget. If you're an academic planning a conference, you likely don't have the enough knowledge that professional event planners have, and it can be easy to misjudge numbers. Super Planner eases the hassle for you by combining all the calculators- staffing, catering, logistics, etc. on a single app. This will help you to keep a track of the budget. Along with simplifying the budget, since the app brings everything on one platform, it saves ample time for the organizers.

6. Bizzabo

Bizzabo is a broad suite of event planning tools in one elegant software package. Targeted medium-to-large-sized businesses; Bizzabo is ideal for planning large events with hefty task demands. The application includes a heavy focus on marketing your event, which makes it great for concerts or telethon.

Event planners can find everything they need to streamline task completion and team collaboration. The software allows you to build event websites for registration, emails for marketing, and agendas for event management.

Conclusion

Events are becoming more prevalent than ever and event management software is what is allowing them to do so. Today's event management platform fulfills a wide range of functions such as event registration, event marketing and reporting. It helps organizers to save time, money, increase security, and reduce chaos. They are reliable, easy-to-use, come with a dedicated customer success team, and should measurably impact your event goals.

From this paper, we can suggest that there should be a set of standards for the events that is conducted. All the affairs coordinated should be of high caliber. It will help in digitalizing the event management organization, which will lead to an increase in the revenue generated from all the events that is organized with the help of digitalization. From this we can conclude that the event management software does more than just managing events—it empowers organizers to unleash the power of live events and ultimately drive event success.

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